

2-Hydroxy-4-methylquinoline-6-arsonic Acid (VI).—Concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was slowly added to the above compound (I; 5 g.), when gradually, on shaking, a thick clear solution was obtained with slight rise in temperature. The solution was then heated in an oil-bath at 60° for 3 hours and then allowed to stand overnight. Next day the solution was poured into ice-water under stirring, when a dark solid was precipitated. This substance is soluble in hot alcohol but it did not show any tendency to crystallise from alcohol. It was, however, purified twice by adding excess of ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance, when an amorphous mass was precipitated, which on standing for about 30 minutes turned into a chocolate-coloured crystalline powder (yield 2 g.), which does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 5.28; As, 26.02. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4NA_s$ requires N, 4.94; As, 26.50 per cent). With ferric chloride an alcoholic solution of this substance does not give any distinctive colouration but gives a brown precipitate. It does not form any phenylhydrazone.

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

Received December 22, 1945.

BISMUTH IODIDE COMPLEXES OF SOME 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

BY S. L. LASKAR

For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, bismuth iodide complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline, 5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, 5:7-dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, 7-iodo-5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline and 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline have been prepared.

In recent years compounds like 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Vioform) and 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Diodoquin) have proved extremely useful in the treatment of chronic and relapsing cases of amoebic dysentery. Emetine bismuth iodide and Kurchi bismuth iodide have also been found to be useful in the treatment of chronic amoebic dysentery. However, as a result of extensive clinical trials of these and other important chemotherapeutic drugs on cases of amoebic dysentery in the army in India, Leishman and Kelsall (*Lancet*, 1944, p. 231) have found that there are some relapsing cases which resist the action of all these drugs or a combination of some of them. They have felt the urgent need for the discovery of a new, more potent amoebicidal drug which will effect cure in chronic and relapsing cases.

In the search for an ideal amoebicidal drug, bismuth iodide complexes of some halogen derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline have now been prepared and characterised. They have been prepared by the interaction of a cold, freshly prepared Dragendorff's reagent with the hydrochloric acid solution of requisite quantity of the respective halogen derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline. All these complex salts are of deep orange colour, soluble in acetone and have definite melting points.

The analyses of the component parts of these complexes have been carried out according to the process adopted in the standardisation of Kurchi bismuth iodide (Mukherjee, *J. & Proc. Inst. of Chem., India*, 1944, 16, 64), slightly modified. In the estimation

of iodine, chloroform has been used in place of alcohol, as the halogenated derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline are less soluble in alcohol than in chloroform.

A study of the data recorded in the Table I (*vide* Experimental) reveals the nature of the composition of these complexes. The percentages of the respective quinoline derivative, bismuth and iodine, as found by analyses, conform to the composition, Q.HI.BiI₃, where Q stands for the corresponding quinoline derivative (*cf.* Quinine bismuth iodide, Franquin and Seguin, *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1925, VIII, I, 525). Moreover, it has been shown by Berg and Wurm (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 1664) that in the estimation of bismuth by using 8-hydroxyquinoline in presence of sulphuric acid and potassium iodide, the complex that separates has also the composition Q.HI.BiI₃. In this connection it may be mentioned that the composition of these complexes, however, differs from that of Kurchi bismuth iodide, which is of the type, B.2HI.BiI₃, where B stands for the base (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The general procedure followed in the preparation of the bismuth iodide complexes of derivatives of 8-hydroxyquinoline is given below in case of one particular preparation. The results of analyses and melting points of other derivatives are summarised in Table I.

8-Hydroxyquinoline-bismuth Iodide.—Pure 8-hydroxyquinoline (2 g.) was dissolved in 10% hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) and the solution was stirred with kaolin for about 30 minutes to remove the colouring matter. After filtration the solution was cooled and to this was slowly added, with constant stirring, freshly prepared, cold Dragendroff's reagent, till the precipitation of an orange-coloured solid was complete. This was filtered, washed several times with water till the filtrate was clear and finally washed with alcohol, dried on the water-bath, m.p. 270-75°; yield 8 g. It is readily soluble in acetone.

TABLE I

Substances	M.p.	% of corresponding quinoline derivatives		Analyses			
		Found.	Calc.	% of Bismuth		% of Iodine	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
8-Hydroxyquinoline bismuth iodide	270-275°	17.00	16.80	24.10	24.21	58.77	58.89
5-Chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline bismuth iodide	225-230°	19.98	20.01	23.32	23.30	56.32	56.60
5 : 7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline bismuth iodide	212-215°	23.01	22.96	22.26	22.42	54.51	54.62
7-Iodo-5 chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline bismuth iodide	190-195°	29.38	29.86	20.61	20.43	50.01	49.71
5 : 7-Diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline bismuth iodide	above 300°	34.77	35.60	18.81	18.74	46.42	45.66

My thanks are due to Dr. T. N. Ghosh for his suggestion in course of this investigation.